

APPROACH TO BIPOLAR DISORDER WITH VARIOUS HEADS

Associate Professor Kürşat Şahin Yıldırım
St. Clements University Vice Dean and Lecturer

St. Clements University Clinical Psychology
Graduate Student Elif Çınar

To cite this article: Elif Çınar, Current Science, Volume 4, No. 8-4, 2022, p. 108 – 133. - 0099-0001-2208-0202.

Our studies are in a format accredited, approved, and supported by EAALS - European Academic Studies and Laboratory Services. EAALS offers all our works, services, and publications to the world scientists at the stage of carrying our control, accreditation, and support processes to the international platform. ("Scientific Studies -Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

Editors Group:

Concessionaire: Tsisana Kharabadze

Dr. Ugur Ugural

Niyaz Bokvadze

Prof. Sabrina Corbi

Prof. Samantha Lewes

Asst. Prof. Osman Doruk

• Current Science Multidisciplinary Academic Journal with Review Panel is a monthly multidisciplinary academic

journal with a multi-science peer-review." ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies -

Current Science Georgia")

• The magazine is published monthly.

"The magazine will be at the subscriber's address in the first week of the month." ("Scientific Studies – Current Science Georgia")

• The journal continues to be included in all international rankings and registrations. Quality articles and publications accelerate this ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") process.

"• Response or rejection time for applications varies between 30 and 90 days." ("Scientific Studies – Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

Abstract

Bipolar disorder is one of the most common psychiatric disorders influencing all population. Untreated bipolar disorder may lead to early death and worsening in general health. Bipolar disorder has several clinically distinct subtypes which are sometimes difficult to diagnose. "Diagnosis and treatment of these disorders are of concern to all other physicians not only psychiatrists, because of their effect on course and prognosis of general medical diseases." ("ÖNEMLİ BİR RUH SAĞLIĞI SORUNU: BİPOLAR BOZUKLUK - DergiPark") The aim of this review article is to investigate an update about etiology, epidemiology, and diagnosis of bipolar disorder.

Low mean scores on the Self-Concept Scale showed that the participants were at risk in terms of mental health. It is recommended that specialist psychiatric nurses, members of mental health teams, conduct practices focused on improving the self-concept of young people who have a parent with bipolar disorder.

Key words: bipolar disorder; causes of bipolar disorder, Investigation of self-concept in the young people of parents with bipolar disorder, bipolar disorder in women, etiology; epidemiology; diagnosis.

1. Introduction:

a. Bipolar Disorder Concept

Bipolar disorder (BD), with its classical definition, is a serious mental disorder that causes depressive, manic, or hypomanic episodes, is completely normal between episodes, or is thought to be accompanied by minimal symptom levels, and is known to cause high mortality, morbidity, and loss of function in every area. . Bipolar disorder

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

is an especially important health problem that used to be assumed to be one percent in lifetime, but in recent years it is estimated to be around five percent when considered as a spectrum. BD has serious social and economic consequences (1). Heterogeneity is mentioned in the definition of bipolar disorder . It should be known that in all patients, the onset of the disease, its timing, course, and response to treatment are related to very complex and multidimensional processes that are not fully understood, and the uncertainty caused by this situation suggests that it is more appropriate to evaluate bipolar disorder as a heterogeneous spectrum rather than a homogeneous disease expressed in the classical definition above. thinks it might be true. The recurrence rate of BB within two years is around 60% (2). For this reason, the implementation of maintenance and preventive treatment in preventing disease periods is of vital importance in these patients. Preventive treatment aimed at preventing relapses and relapses and cutting sub-threshold symptoms reduces mortality and morbidity and increases the quality of life of patients (1,3). In this multifaceted self-review study, the etiology, epidemiology, causes, diagnosis, and clinical presentation of bipolar disorder are discussed in the light of current and various information, to emphasize once again how important bipolar disorder is as a health problem and to compile the information in a succinct manner . targeted.

b - Definition of Bipolar Disorder

Bipolar disorder is a chronic mood disorder that is characterized by recurrent episodes of mania, hypomania, depression, or mixed mood, leading to significant impairment in occupational, familial, and social functionality (Maj M, Akiskal HS, Lopez-Ibor JJ, Sartorius N. Bipolar Disorders. West Sussex, UK, Wiley, 2002.).

c -History of Bipolar Disorder

1. Aretus defined bipolar disorder in the most contemporary way. The concept of mood, which we meet in many pages of psychology, also appears in the history of bipolar disorder. The fact that mood and mood changes in humans can be seen from the

outside has been one of the subjects of interest since ancient times. The origin of the word melancholy, which is still used today, comes from the words "melas", that is, "black", and "kole", that is, "gall", and in the time of Hippocrates (fifth century BC), the clinical situation in which negative emotions such as lack of energy, hopelessness, sadness, and nervousness were seen together. used to express. In the same period, the word mania was used to express the enthusiastic state that occurs with the increase for yellow bile in the body. Although it does not have an agreed-upon origin as in melancholy, it is thought to be derived from the ancient Greek words "Ania" or "Manos" (Angst J, Marneros A. Bipolarity from ancient to modern times: conception, birth, and rebirth. *J Affect Disord* .2001;67 (1-3):3-19.). The word mania was met in mythological literature before the Hippocratic era, but there was no semantic consistency between them as it was in the Hippocratic era. In terms of the clinical course of bipolar disorder, the first person to describe it, albeit is Aretus from Cappadocia. Aretus realized in the middle of the second century AD that mania and melancholy could be seen in the same person at various times (5). Soranus also drew attention to a similar connection between melancholy and mania (6). At the beginning of the 11th century, Ibn Sina has case studies on the subject. Not much has been said about it from those ages until the 19th century. When we come to the beginning of the 19th century, "lypomania", which is one of the affective monomanias defined by Esquirol, bears great similarities with the clinical symptoms of depression today (7). At the beginning of 1854, Baillarger and Falret presented the same clinical picture with two different names to the French medical academic board, with two weeks apart; presented them as "biphasic mental illness" and "cyclical mental illness", respectively (8,9). The clinical presentation described is periodic periods of mania and depression in the same patient. According to Oral reported; In 1862, Griesenger said that mania and depression are part of a single illness. Kahlbaum defined cyclothymia in 1882, and Kraepelin, based on this concept in 1895, defined today's bipolar spectrum diseases for the first time as "manic depressive psychosis" with many different clinical manifestations (10). In the 1930s, Bleuler named these clinical pictures as "affective disorders" (10). According to

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

Goodwin and Jamison (1990); Based on Meyer's view that mania and depression are affected by the brain's response to psychological and social stimuli, "manic depressive reaction" was first defined in the DSM-I (Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders) developed by the American Psychiatric Association (APA) in 1952. definition was used (11). The same authors also mentioned Leonard's concepts of bipolar (having manic and depressive episodes) and monopolar (having only depression or only manic episodes) disorders in 1959 (11). After these terms came into use, only those with manic episodes were included in the definition of bipolar disorder, while patients with only depressive episodes were called "unipolar". In 1976, Dunner suggested that the disease be divided into two subtypes as Bipolar 1 and Bipolar 2 (12). In DSM-III, major depression and bipolar disorder were defined as two separate disorders that fall under affective disorders, and in DSM-III-R, the definition of affective disorders was renamed as mood disorders to express a more inclusive and general condition. BD, which is included in mood disorders in DSM-IV and DSM-IV-R, was discussed as bipolar and related disorders in DSM-5 published in 2013 (13).

2. Epidemiology of Bipolar Disorder

Innovation, developments, and changes are reflected in this field. As the information about the nature of BPD is renewed and it is understood that it is not a disease with a benign course as previously thought, its place and importance among mental health diseases and, accordingly, scientific studies and publications in the fields of the disease have increased (3,4,5). One of these areas is the epidemiology of BD. In a follow-up study conducted in Nigeria about 10 years ago, the lifetime prevalence of bipolar disorder was reported to be 1%, except for the low 0.1% reported in countries such as India, Bulgaria, and Romania (14). However, new publications; It shows that this rate rises to 6.4% when the patients with bipolar spectrum diseases and sub-threshold duration or severity symptoms are included, who are evaluated as patients in routine clinical conditions and who need treatment and benefit from treatment (15). In the National Epidemiological Monitoring study conducted in the United States (USA),

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

rates were given as 0.8% for BD type 1, 0.5% for BD type 2, and 0.8-1% for cyclothymia (16). In another study conducted later and published by the National Comorbidity Monitoring group in the USA in 2007, the prevalence rate was 1% for BD type 1 and 1% for BD type 2. 1, and 2.4% for people with subthreshold symptoms (14,17). In another study conducted in 2011, these rates were reported as 0.6% for BD type 1, 0.4% for BD type 2, and 2.4% for those with sub-threshold symptoms (17). Contrary to major depression, there is no significant difference in the distribution of bipolar disorder between genders. However, when the features of bipolar disorder are detailed apart from the diagnostic partnership, areas where there are significant differences between men and women emerge. For example, it has been reported that mixed episodes, manic shift triggered by antidepressants, rapid cycling, added medical problems, and substance abuse are more common in women than in men, psychotic features are more common in women, and the frequency of depressive episodes increases with age (18,19). It is known that the age of onset of BD type 2 is a little later and it is more common in women (20). In a study, the rate of men who had only manic episodes without having a depressive episode was 38.9%, while this rate was 4.1% for women (21). It has been reported that seasonal characteristics, atypical clinical factors, and total time spent in depression are much higher in women, but when gay people are considered as a subtype in men, these parameters are at similar levels to those in women (20). The age of onset of BD is accepted as 17-25 years old. The mean age has been reported as 24.8 years for women and 24.4 years for men (22). In another study, the mean age of onset was eighteen for BD type 1 and 22 for BD type 2 (23). It is estimated that the disease starts 4-5 years earlier in men than in women (20). The age of onset of the disease is under twenty in almost half of the BD patients. In another publication evaluating the age of onset, it was reported that approximately 30% of the patients started to have symptoms before the age of 21 and 10% after the age of 50 (24). BD type 2 is thought to have a late onset. It has been reported that mixed episodes are more frequent in early-onset BD type 1 (25). In follow-up studies in the USA, it has been seen that the age of onset has been decreasing for both BD type 1 and type 2 (26).

Giving birth at an early age in women can put the onset of the disease forward if there is a predisposition to the disease. Care should be taken in terms of the diagnosis of BD in patients who have had depression in the postpartum period, because the rate of BD diagnosis in this patient group is quite high (25). When the subject is considered in terms of race and ethnicity, different epidemiological data in some countries are explained mostly through methodological and socioeconomic texture differences (17-19). Therefore, despite the differences in current prevalence rates, there is a consensus that there is no racial difference in the prevalence of bipolar disorder in the community. The presence of a family history is a common condition for this disease from Kraepelin to the present. About 120 years ago, Kraepelin noted that the disease was more common in relatives of maniac-depressive psychosis patients, and that some "weird" behavior patterns might even be common in relatives who might even be considered healthy. In this context, the genetic burden of the disease is an issue that has been noticed and emphasized for a long time.

For a long time, BD has been thought to be more common in individuals with a high socioeconomic status. In epidemiological studies, the low prevalence rates seen in some countries were explained by the low socioeconomic level of that country rather than the ethnic disease burden (27). Although lower rates of disease have been seen in societies with lower socioeconomic status, impairment in functionality and annual loss of workdays are higher in sick individuals in these societies, which is explained by the limited treatment opportunities in these societies. In societies that consume seafood rich in omega three content and fatty acids (such as Hong Kong, Taiwan), the disease is less common (28). It is thought that the disease is more common in divorced or separated individuals, but it would be more reasonable to explain this data simply because of the patient's impaired functionality (28). However, the view that this disease is more common in singles is shared by many clinicians (29). When the disease was evaluated in terms of seasonal characteristics, it was seen that manias tended to occur in the summer months and depressions tended to occur in the spring months in one third of the patients. It is thought that both seasonal characteristics and suicidal rates

accumulated in certain periods decrease in these patients with electroconvulsive therapy (ECT) or drug treatments (20). Bipolar Disorder is often associated with other Axis I and Axis II disorders, and 25-50% of patients try suicide once in their lifetime and 15% die because of suicide attempt (28). It may apply to the people of the northern hemisphere ; It is widely believed that mania rates increase as you get closer to the equator, and depression rates increase as you get farther away. Disease rates, which tend to increase slightly when we go from east to west, are explained by sociocultural and methodological differences in related studies (20). Although the effect of the personality structure of the individual before the disease on the disease is not clear, it has been suggested that depression is associated with elevated levels of neuroticism and negative emotionality, and hypomania and manias are associated with elevated levels of positive emotionality (30).

3. Etiology of Bipolar Disorder

When we look at the etiology of bipolar disorder, it is thought that many varied factors play a role in different and unpredictable severity. In fact, this is a branching and deep field that needs to be dealt with in a single book, in a single book, and even in a field where innovations are added every day.

The etiology of bipolar disorder is the most important part of this study. These factors can be examined under two different headings as biological and environmental factors:

4. Bipolar Disorder and Biological Factors

a . Effect of Genetic Factor

The results of many studies have shown that while bipolar disorder is more common in some regions, it is less common in some regions. It has been known for over a century that this disease is seen more often in some families and has an especially important hereditary aspect (31). This importance has been confirmed in all special studies on the subject, albeit at different rates. In the literature, there are many families,

twin, adoption, chromosomal region, and candidate gene studies related to BD inheritance. In terms of heredity, the recent linkage and association studies, especially in molecular genetics, are very promising. It has been reported that genetic factors may have a weight of 60-80% in the development of bipolar disorder (32). Today, the risk of BD in individuals with a first-degree relative with the disease has been found to be between 3-8%, which shows that family history is an independent variable that alone can increase the risk of the disease 4-8 times (20). If both parents are sick, the risk of disease rises to 50-75% (26). In adoption studies, it was found that the biological parents of children with bipolar disorder were three times more likely to have bipolar disorder than the adoptive parents (30). In a study, it was found that the risk of developing the disease increased ten times and the risk of developing major depression increased three times in individuals with a first-degree relative with BD (34). In twin studies related to BD type 1, it was found that the gene concordance between monozygotic siblings for the disease was approximately 40% in monozygotic twins and approximately 5% in fraternal twins (35). When unipolar depression is included, the rate increases to 67% to 90% in monozygotes and 19% to 23% in dizygotes. The fact that the concordance rate is not 100% in monozygotic twins shows that psycho-social etiological factors are also important. In a study on twin siblings in which both patients and patients were followed up, the risk of developing BD in their children was found to be equal (36). **According to Uluşahin (2004)**; The first genetic linkage study related to mania was made in 1969 (37). The linkage studies that started about 25 years ago on the X chromosome and the 11th chromosome in Amish, and which aroused great excitement, continued in chromosomes such as 5 and 18, and there were studies emphasizing that a division in 18p may manage the disease clinic to a considerable extent (37). Also in the literature, Monoamine oxidase A (MAO-A), 5HTT(5-hydroxytryptophan), Catechol-O-methyltransferase (COMT), Gammaaminobutyric acid (GABA) sub-receptor types, corticotropin-releasing hormone (CRH), adenosine A1, serotonin receptor sub-receptor There are association studies related to the types (38). However, although there are many promising studies, repeated studies did not

yield consistent results. A large genome-association-linkage study conducted in 2013 revealed that no single gene or gene region plays a single or highly predominant role in the development of the disease (39). Currently, the prevailing view on this issue is that genetic transition is provided polymorphic with a large number of genes, and this occurs by being affected by environmental factors at a certain level. Despite the contradictory results, studies in this area will still be continued.

5. Beginning of Genetic Studies

Genetic studies conducted all over the world shed light on bipolar disorder. Family, twin, and adopted child studies were the first steps in the genetic investigation of bipolar disorder, with the prevalence of the disease being decided in the community and the greater research interest in the disease because of its higher-than-expected prevalence. In 1996, Lewinsohn et al. In their study on high school children using the “Schedule for Affective Disorders and Schizophrenia for School-aged children (K-SADS)” screening test, they found a 1% prevalence, mostly bipolar II and cyclothymia. In the same study, the rate of adolescent individuals with subsyndromal symptoms was found to be 5.7% (3). In the prevalence studies conducted in the following years, the incidence of the disease was found to be close to these levels. The high **incidence of the disease in parents and relatives of children with bipolar disorder in adults or children of natural parents was the starting point showing the importance of genetic etiology.** In the studies, the incidence of BD in the children of individuals with the disease was found to be **exactly seven times higher than in healthy children** . This risk is not only for BB. The incidence of BD was found to be higher in the children of individuals with depression, conduct disorder, disruptive behavior disorder and anxiety disorders compared to healthy individuals (4). The incidence of the disease in the children of individuals with BD was found to be 5.7% (5). In the past years, genetic studies started late, since it was predicted that the probability of BB in the pediatric group was low. In a retrospective study on better describing pediatric-onset BD, 60% of adults with BD diagnosed before the age of twenty; It has been found that 10%-20%

have symptoms before the age of 10 (6). In studies conducted in the adult age group, it was revealed that BD symptoms were present up to 10 years before the definitive diagnosis. Family studies on BD were generally conducted in the 1970s, and there are data showing that the incidence of BD is 2-4 times higher in the presence of a family history of BD. Twin Studies In addition to familial genetic transmission studies, twin individual studies have been an important source of data on the genetic transmission of all diseases in medicine; It is one of the only sources we have to determine how effective genetic factors are compared to environmental factors . If we understand and think that genetics plays a key role in the basis of a disease, high concordance (co-morbidity) is expected in monozygotic studies. Single egg and fraternal cases also showed their differences in this regard. In studies conducted on BD, the concordance of the disease is 70%-90% in identical twins, while the rate in fraternal twins is 16%-35% (10). It is noteworthy that twin studies on this subject are very few and belong to the past years. This may be related to the low number of patients diagnosed with pediatric BD in the past, and the low probability of finding twins in the patient group with a low sample number; It may also be related to the fact that genetic examination of these patients was not preferred much in the past years in today's clinical practice, where BD is diagnosed more easily.

b. Could Calcium Channel Antagonists Be Involved in the Treatment of Bipolar Disorder in the Future?

Studies on this subject can enlighten us clearly. CACNA1C (voltage dependent calcium channel gene)-1c subunit (12th chromosome), ANK3 (Ankrin, 10). . chromosome), two different genome regions on chromosome twelve, SYNE1 (spectrin protein close to the nuclear membrane), ODZ4 (11th chromosome) gene regions were significantly associated with BD (19). Voltage-dependent calcium channels are effective in calcium influx into neurons and indirectly play a role in neuronal plasticity and neuronal transcription. Significant association in the CACNA1C gene may be a

clue for neuronal pathology in BD. In the past years, there are studies showing that calcium channel antagonists such as nimodipine, which have good blood-brain barrier penetration, are used in the prevention, delay, and treatment of BB attacks (20). The ANK3 gene encodes spectrin-ankyrin proteins involved in the formation of the cytoskeleton. Ankrin proteins belong to the family of intracellular integral proteins and play a key role in functions such as cell motility, proliferation, and cell communication. Ankrin 3 (Ankrin G) gene region; In the central and peripheral nervous system, it is considered separately from Ankrin 1 and Ankrin 2 due to its high abundance in the axon initiation (initial) region and nodes of Ranvier. Ankrin 3, also known as ankrin G protein, connects voltage-dependent channels to the axon body and indirectly influences action potential generation. The SYNE1 gene region (spectrin repeat having, nuclear envelope 1) encodes a protein having spectrin repeats near the nuclear membrane in peripheral blood lymphocytes, skeletal and striated muscle cells. Previously, there are suspicions that it may be associated with diseases such as autosomal recessive spinocerebellar ataxia and autosomal recessive cerebellar ataxia (21). The ODZ4 gene region is found on chromosome eleven and encodes a cell surface protein called teneurin. Studies on the critical roles of teneurin proteins in cell communication, oligodendrocyte differentiation, and myelination of nerves in the central nervous system have begun to be published in literature (22). These differing gene regions have raised suspicions that the disease mechanism may be related with mechanisms quite different from the limbic system receptors and neurotransmitters that contribute to the regulation of emotion. In a recent meta-analysis, 4 of 18 genes examined in 3 or more studies out of 487 articles published until 2009 were found to be significantly associated with BD. Associated genes: BDNF gene (Brain derived neurotrophic factor) DRD4 gene (Dopamine receptor D4) DAOA gene (D-amino acid oxidase activator) TPH1 gene (Tryptophan hydroxylase) (2) Although 4 genes are significant in this meta-analysis, psychiatric disorders described in 2009 inconsistency with the genomic consortium study data stands out.

c . Discussion and Results on Genetic Factors

Man is a special and complex being. So, to speak, the tree did not come out of the hollow. He carries the effects of his lineage in every health problem. While some genetic aspects of bipolar disorder are clear and unequivocal, some issues are still under discussion. Bipolar disorder is a chronic illness with recurrent periods of mania, hypomania, mixed and depression. Considering the frequency of occurrence, clinical features, and the high familial incidence of the disease in children and adolescents, it became inevitable to examine it in terms of genetics. There is debate on the etiology. Genetic factors, environmental factors, neurobiological and hormonal factors, neurochemical factors are mentioned, and research are conducted. The etiology of BB is still not fully elucidated. It is now considered to be seen in childhood and adolescence. Genetic factors, environmental factors, neurobiological and hormonal factors, neurochemical factors are mentioned in the etiology of this disease. In recent years, the genetic aspect of the disease has gained more importance and started to be investigated, and in this article, it is aimed to discuss the results obtained by reviewing the articles evaluating the genetic aspect of BD in children and adolescents. The genetic research adventure, which started with family, twin and adopted child studies related to BD, has reached the genome level due to the elevated level of technological opportunities . Although all studies have revealed that the genetic transmission of BD is too large to be ignored, the results of the studies are inconsistent with each other. Current studies are in the form of multi-sample and multicenter studies; There is a lack of research in the pediatric age group. Due to the abundance of studies with conflicting results, it is still not possible to explain the pathophysiology of the disease at the genetic level. Although genes related to the limbic system such as SLC6A4, 5HTT, HTR2A, DRD2 have been studied before, recent studies have moved away from the limbic system because the results of the research are not repetitive; It also concentrates on the calcium channel system in the neuron. Studies on the calcium channel system are limited; There are limitations about age group, method, and similar features. BD is a psychiatric disorder that is known to have genetic origins like many psychiatric diseases such as

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

schizophrenia, autism, ADHD, and obsessive-compulsive disorder, but has not been clearly clarified in terms of genetics yet, and therefore the reasons for its formation have not been discovered yet. When the literature on the subject is examined, it is thought that genetic studies to be conducted in the coming years will be in a wide range.

6. Bipolar Disorder and Biochemical Factors

Despite numerous studies, little is known about the pathophysiology of BD. Until now, the investigation of biochemical causes has focused on the monoaminergic system, including serotonin, noradrenaline and, to a lesser extent, dopamine. Especially in the formation of mania, noradrenergic activation, imbalance between "Noradrenergic-cholinergic" systems and cholinergic insufficiency are mentioned (40). Ltryptophan, a precursor of serotonin, creates a mania-like picture when given in high doses (5,6). Serotonin has a significant regulatory role in functions such as sleep-wake, desire to eat, libido, and body temperature. Serotonin, together with adrenaline and dopamine, takes an active role in purposeful motor functions and in the restriction of aggressive behaviors (5). There is stimulation in dopaminergic system activity in mania (41). It has been suggested that depression occurs with a decrease in monoamines, and mania with an increase in monoamines (5). Other major neurotransmitters thought to play a role in the etiology are acetylcholine, GABA, and glutamate (41). It has been reported that synaptic release of acetylcholine is related to depression and its decrease is related to mania (42). It is thought that amino acid neurotransmitters such as GABA and especially neuroactive peptides such as vasopressin and endogenous opiates play a role in the pathophysiology of mood disorders (43).

7. Brain Imaging:

The findings obtained with brain imaging may not have etiological significance, and the presence of contradictory findings because of studies prevents these results from being generalizable. Among the main brain imaging findings, enlargement of the

lateral ventricles, increased hyperintensity in deep white matter and subcortical gray matter areas, decrease in ventroparietal frontal cortex cell density, increase, or decrease in amygdala volume, decrease in hippocampus volume, increase in hyperintense lesions in basal ganglia or decrease in glial cells (44).

8. Bipolar 1 Bipolar 2 Cross-sectional View

There are two subtypes of bipolar disorder, as it is understandable and in common parlance; If the person has had at least one manic episode, bipolar disorder type 1 is diagnosed, and if he has had at least one depression and hypomania, he is diagnosed with bipolar disorder type 2. People with bipolar 2 will experience less severe manic episodes than those with bipolar 1 . This type of mania is known as hypomania. To be diagnosed with bipolar two, a person must also have had a major depressive episode that does not qualify for a diagnosis of bipolar one. As I mentioned before, people who are prone to bipolar disorder due to their genetic heritage may develop discomfort with the effects of triggers such as stressful life events. It is known that factors such as genetic inheritance, brain structure, development and neurotransmitter that provides intercellular communication are effective in the development of bipolar disorder. Bipolar one and bipolar two disorder are the most common types of bipolar disorder. Everyone experiences emotional difficulties from time to time. But if you have a condition called bipolar disorder, these emotional difficulties can reach abnormal levels. Sometimes you may feel extremely excited or energetic, and sometimes you may feel depressed. These emotional difficulties can last for weeks or months.

9. Neuroendocrine System:

Disturbance in thyroid function tests (such as hyperthyroidism, hypothyroidism) and endocrine anomalies such as hypercortisolemia (such as Cushing's disease) and many neurological diseases (such as Multiple Sclerosis (MS), stroke, temporal lobe

epilepsy, brain tumors, dementia) and head traumas like bipolar disorder they can lead to clinical pictures (45).

10. Bipolar Disorder and Environmental Factors

Speaking of so many genetics, it would be unwise to skip environmental factors. It is a fact that environmental factors affect the emergence and course of the disease. Even in the absence of genetic factors that increase the susceptibility to the disease, some lifestyle habits, **alcohol and substance use, some drugs taken from outside and psychosocial factors** may play a key role in the development or worsening of the disease. Although the presence of psychosocial factors in the later years of the disease is not associated with the onset of seizures, it is thought that manic or depressive psychosocial developments and stressful life events are important triggering factors, especially for the first seizures. However, this relationship weakens as the number of earlier mood episodes and familial genetic load increase (20). In women, especially the perinatal period carries a significant risk for the onset of disease. Seasonally, periods of increased **exposure to sunlight** are associated with the appearance of manic or subthreshold symptoms (46).

11. Diagnosis and Clinical Appearance

A chronic disease that leads to impaired functionality, unfortunately increases the risk of suicide, and can bring serious comorbidities and complications . In this context, it is vital to diagnose the disease as quickly and accurately as possible. In recent studies, it was reported that 69% of bipolar disorder patients were misdiagnosed in their first outpatient clinic admission (47), and in another study, approximately 10 years passed before these patients received their current diagnosis (48). Considering that half of the patients do not seek treatment within the first 5 years, the size of the problems that may be caused by a delay in diagnosis can be better understood (46,47). Two systems used in the diagnosis and classification of mental disorders; It is the DSM developed by the American Psychiatric Association (APA) and the ICD (International

Statistical Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems) developed by the World Health Organization (WHO). The most significant difference between DSM-IV-TR and ICD-10 is the absence of BD type 1 and type 2 distinction in ICD. According to DSM-IV, a single manic episode is sufficient for the diagnosis of BD type 1 (49). For BD type 2, at least one hypomanic and depressive episode must have been experienced. In DSM-5 published in 2013, unlike DSM-IVTR, BD was discussed under the title of "Bipolar and Associated Disorders", mixed episode was abolished, mixed feature was used as a marker in manic or depressive episodes and replaced with "mixed mania/hypomania". or a depressive episode (13).

12. Self-Design of Teens with Bipolar Parents

The average age of the young people between the ages of 15-25 taking part in the research is 19.83±3.02. The average of the scores of the young people from the self-concept scale is 3.54±41.26. (Cashwell C, Nasson S. Building self-esteem of children and adolescents. Journal of Humanistic Education & Development 1997;36:59–68.) The socioeconomic status of young people with bipolar disorder, including age, gender, educational status, marital status, and family structure. - while there was no significant difference between the mean scores of the self-design scale according to their demographic characteristics; A significant difference was found between the mean scores of the self-concept scale according to the income level and support status of the youth. It was found that the young people with high income level got higher scores from the self-concept scale compared to the young people with low-income level. It was found that the young people who received support from their grandparents other than their parents while growing up had higher scores on the self-concept scale. As a result, the low self-concept score averages of young people whose parents have bipolar disorder show that they are a risky group in terms of mental health. It is recommended that specialist psychiatric nurses, who are members of the mental health team, should

conduct studies focusing on the positive development of self-concepts of young people whose parents have bipolar disorder.

It was found that there was no significant difference between the mean scores of the self-concept scale according to the gender, educational status, marital status, and family structure of the young people whose parents had bipolar disorder. On the other hand, it was found that there was a significant difference between the mean scores of the self-concept scale according to the income level of the youth ($t=3.65$; $p=0.029<0.05$). It was decided that the mean scores of the self-concept scale were lower among the young people with low income compared to those with high income levels. While 51.9% of the parents of the young people who took part in the study with bipolar disorder were their mothers, 48.1% were their fathers. It was found that there was no significant difference between the mean scores of the self-concept scale ($p=0.246>0.05$) according to the characteristics of being a mother or father of the parent with bipolar disorder (Table 2). It was found that there was a significant difference between the self-concept scale mean scores of the young people, according to the presence of people other than their parents who contributed significantly to the upbringing of young people whose parents had bipolar disorder.

Compared to the samples formed by the young people whose parents do not have the disease, it is seen that the self-concept score average of the young people whose parents have bipolar disorder is much lower. Considering that a parent has a mental illness or bipolar disorder, the child's secure attachment to his parents, developing self-confidence, fulfilling his physical and social responsibilities, and being effective in the formation of self-concept[19,20], it can be thought that young people will negatively affect their self-concepts. . The fact that the mean scores of the self-concept of the youth whose parents had bipolar disorder were lower than those who had no parents with the illness shows that the self-concepts of this group need to be improved in a positive way. To increase self-concepts in a positive way, it is thought that it is important to be supported by mental health specialists and psychiatric nurses to conduct studies for this purpose.

13. Progression in Bipolar Disorder

We also need to have foresight to know exactly how a situation is progressing. As mentioned before, the course of BD is an almost unpredictable disease. However, although it is difficult to make future predictions for a single diseased individual, there are also patterns seen in multi-sample studies and statistical variables with clinical significance. For example, approximately 90% of patients diagnosed with BD have relapses and relapses. This gives us the opportunity to talk to the relatives of the patients who are curious and worried about the future of their patients, about the 90% probability that the disease may recur (50). Another statistic that appears from one of the studies with a large sample size is that there is an average of 0.6 periods in a year (51). It is thought that variables such as age, age of onset, functionality related to life before the disease, and gender, which are thought to provide clues for the clinical course, do not have a significant effect, however, variables such as the frequency and severity of past episodes, and response to treatment are effective (52). The presence of psychotic symptoms, comorbid personality disorder, and substance abuse are considered poor prognostic indicators. Mixed episodes and psychotic features may also show a poor prognosis. It is thought that the disease first appears in the form of depression (50%-85%). If the first episode is early-onset and manic, familial burden may be considered. It has been reported that after a period, the probability of recurrence may increase to 50% within one year, to 70% within four years, and up to 90% within five years (53). While depressive episodes begin with insidious and usually preliminary symptoms, mania begins abruptly. There are publications reporting that depressive episodes subside in an average of 3-5 months, manic episodes in an average of 2 months, and mixed episodes in an average of 5-12 months (54-56). Periodic cycles are thought to get shorter as time passes. In one study, it was emphasized that patients with residual symptoms after the period experienced relapses within the first six months (57). While the presence of environmental factors and triggers is mentioned at the beginning of the

disease (47 percent of early manias occur after an important life event), later disease periods may occur independently of these triggers (53). Patients with postpartum depression should be carefully checked in terms of BD in the future. Because it has been reported that cases with a diagnosis of postpartum depression were followed up with a diagnosis of BD in the following years (54). According to DSM, the clinical course determinants were grouped under two headings: markers describing the last period and the course of recurrent episodes. Indicators describing the last period; While there are features such as severity of symptoms, chronicity, presence of catatonic, melancholic or atypical features, and postpartum onset, markers defining the course of recurrent periods; It is characterized by complete and partial recovery or no improvement in longitudinal follow-ups, seasonal or rapid cycling characteristics. Roughly speaking, the treatment approach of the disease, which progresses in the form of manic or depressive periods and euthymic periods, will vary according to the disease period of the patient. For example, when the terms manic episode or depressive episode are used for these patients, what is meant is the period from the onset of symptoms to the point of complete resolution of the symptoms. The treatment applied during this period is also called acute treatment. Acute periods last for an average of 6-12 weeks. The whole disease, on the other hand, continues for a lifetime with a widely accepted point of view. van der Voort et al. (2015), only 24% of patients can make a full recovery (55).

14. Treatment and Basic Principles

Bipolar disorder is a mental disorder that should be emphasized in terms of its prevalence and the size of the functional destruction it causes. 10 to 20% of patients with a diagnosis of BD die because of a suicide attempt (56). This importance can be better understood when the medical problems and even deaths that may be indirectly caused by the damage to the organ systems caused by the side effects of the drugs used for treatment are considered. In this context, carefully planned and integrated acute treatment, maintenance treatment and preventive treatment programs can be lifesaving.

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

A field study showed that approximately 40% of patients with BD did not receive any treatment (20). It is imperative for the clinician to make an early diagnosis and start treatment simultaneously, and to be flexible in choosing drugs according to the treatment response. The first step in BB treatment belongs to the acute period. Objectives of acute mania treatment; controlling risky behaviors, ensuring the safety of the patient and the environment, relieving symptoms, and preparing for preventive treatment to prevent new periods of illness. The main drugs in the treatment of acute mania are mood stabilizers, especially lithium. In the acute phase, benzodiazepines and antipsychotics can be added to the treatment for a certain period. Whether the patient has euphoric or mixed mania should be considered in the selection of drugs. Valproate is preferred in rapid cycling, mixed mania, and psychotic mania (1,27). Antipsychotics and benzodiazepines can be added to the treatment, especially in patients with severe agitation where rapid control is needed. ECT is recommended in resistant cases and during pregnancy. When the manic picture improves, antipsychotics are dropped, and mood stabilizers are continued. The aim of bipolar depressive episode treatment is to take the patient out of depression in the most effective and fastest possible, considering the risk of suicide (47,58). While aiming for the recovery of depression, concerns should be taken against processes such as manic shift and cycle acceleration, and precautions should be kept at the highest level. The inclusion of mood stabilizers in the treatment is especially important, especially against manic shift and cycle acceleration. In classical cases, the first choice is lithium. In severe and unresponsive cases, antidepressants and/or lamotrigine are added to the treatment. It is recommended to start antidepressants at a low dose, use the lowest effective dose, and not continue antidepressant treatment for a long time. More selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs) are preferred. ECT is applied in severe, catatonic, or psychotic depression and in pregnant women (58). In bipolar disorder, after the acute period treatment, maintenance treatment is started. The aim of maintenance therapy is to prevent depressive shifts, relapses, and relapses. In patients with risk factors such as family history, starting preventive treatment directly after the first mood episode is a more

accepted approach than waiting for the next period to come, and a consensus is reached. However, although the right treatment approach, including preventive treatment, can be lifesaving, as said above, it is not an effortless process for patients and their relatives to adapt. Mood stabilizers used in preventive treatment can sometimes create side effects that lead to changes in the patient's life that he perceives negatively and disrupt drug compliance (1). Considering the use of multiple drugs and the frequency of daily dose intervals, which we sometimes must choose preventive treatment in practice, drug compliance can be an especially important problem for the patient. Therefore, psychoeducation to be given to patients and their relatives for preventive treatment is important in terms of increasing treatment compliance.

15. Main Principles in the Treatment of Bipolar Disorder

1. Making a definitive diagnosis of the disease and preparing the basis for treatment
 2. Deciding on options such as intensive inpatient or outpatient treatment based on the clinical presentation of the episode
 3. Assessing general safety or suicide risks, if necessary, obtaining information from third parties or institutions and deepening the story
 4. Establishing and keeping a therapeutic relationship with the patient
 5. Educating the patient and his family
 6. Focusing on both acute treatment and preventive treatment without seeing one as more important than the other.
 7. Charting both retrospective and prospective disease
 8. Evaluate and correct impairment in functionality
- * Retrieved from Goodwin and Jamison (2007).

(59) . Rates of up to 64% are reported for non-adherence to the preventive treatment of bipolar disorder (47). Especially in our society, since mood episodes are perceived as a situation that a person can cope with or must cope with alone, rather than a disease, it is a necessity to explain the current situation to the patients and their relatives and to explain the necessity of preventive treatment.

16. Early Intervention in Bipolar Disorder

In the last century, physicians have been searching for early intervention strategies to prevent or at least improve the course of all diseases. There is an increasing interest in the early or prodromal period findings of psychiatric diseases. A growing body of data on the progressive nature of bipolar disorder suggests that milder episodes of illness may precede the onset of illness. In fact, it is known that 50-70% of bipolar disorder patients show mood symptoms before the age of twenty-one. For this reason, early intervention ways and strategies that will minimize cognitive, social, and professional disability are of immense importance. Vieta, E, Salagre E, Grande I, Carvalho AF, Fernandes BS, Berk M. & Suppes T. (2018)

17. Risk Factors: Predicting the Development of Bipolar Disorder

Everything that happened in childhood comes out under this title. Bipolar disorder is a multifactorial disease. Studies in terms of environmental factors have yielded contradictory results about the effect of life events on the development of bipolar disorder. Childhood sexual abuse has been proven to be associated with poor prognosis. Antidepressant use in adolescents may also be a risk factor. Again, substance abuse worsens the prognosis and increases the risk of developing bipolar disorder in patients followed up with a diagnosis of depression and anxiety disorder.

The effect of genetic factors in the development of bipolar disorder is indisputable, family history increases the risk of developing bipolar disorder. In particular, the diagnosis of early-onset (before the age of 21) bipolar disorder by parents is the biggest risk factor for the development of bipolar disorder in their children. From a neurodevelopmental perspective, it was found that while the risk of developing mania increased in children with low Denver scores, the risk of depression and psychosis did not change. Interestingly, there is a study that shows that children with high academic achievement have the highest risk of developing bipolar disorder.

18. Prodromal Symptoms

In a study conducted in Denmark, the first presentation of 88% of children diagnosed with bipolar disorder to be diagnosed with bipolar disorder in the future was with a depressive episode, and the mean time for conversion to bipolar disorder after the first episode was 5.1 years. The presence of sub-threshold (hypo)manic symptoms is the most important predictor of the development of (hypo)manic episodes in both the general population, the high-risk group, and the children of individuals diagnosed with bipolar disorder. Among the individuals diagnosed with bipolar disorder, the risk of getting sick is 49% in the children of those with affective lability and hypomanic symptoms. In the general population, hypomanic symptoms or affective lability at an early age increase the risk of developing bipolar disorder in the future. The bipolar disorder prodromal

symptom scale and the early bipolar disorder scale can be used for risk assessment. The Pittsburg study of bipolar children developed a risk estimation system that included dimensions of mania, depression, anxiety, affective lability, psychosocial functioning, and age of onset of parental bipolar disorder.

19. Predicting Bipolar Disorder with Biomarkers

Neuroimaging and peripheral biomarker studies have yielded conflicting results, findings are not specific to bipolar disorder and studies with larger samples are needed. For now, we can say that a single biomarker is not enough to predict risk and more studies are needed.

20. What to Do in Early Intervention?

Psychotherapeutic Interventions

therapy, which combines psychoeducation with communication and problem-solving skills, is the only psychological early intervention method studied on the development of bipolar disorder. This method was associated with longer affective stability and milder symptom levels in high-risk children. In this approach, a symptom-

and problem-focused approach is recommended rather than disease . Social rhythm therapy and multifamily psychoeducational psychotherapy, interpersonal and social rhythm therapies also have limited but promising effects in reducing disease development rate and disease severity. Social rhythm therapy is in the realm that people do not fully know yet. Psychotherapy has made progress in this area by giving serious struggles.

A PTSD (World Health Organization 2013) where EMDR was selected among the more proper treatments by WHO.

While available studies on the application of EMDR in bipolar disorders are currently really few, the conclusions of each presented study seem to agree on some points: EMDR appears to be a promising treatment for related trauma affective symptoms and relapse. Prevention: In fact, EMDR seems to elicit some positive effects that are truly relevant in the therapeutic process of this psychopathological condition, including treatment adherence and disease awareness in bipolar patients. (Bedeschi, Ludovica)

Feske and Goldsteina (1997) randomized forty-three patients diagnosed with panic disorder with agoraphobia to either EMDR Therapy, eye fixation exposure and reprocessing therapy, or a waiting list. Patients received five sessions of 120 minutes, four of which were 90 minutes, every 3 weeks. When the posttests of the patients receiving EMDR Therapy were compared with the posttests of the waiting list group, it was found that the patients with a diagnosis of anxiety disorder who received EMDR Therapy made considerable progress.

The effectiveness of EMDR Therapy in unipolar mood disorder was investigated (Behnammoghadam et al., 2015). Sixty patients diagnosed with depression received EMDR therapy for 45-60 minutes every week for 4 months, and the control group did not receive any psychotherapeutic intervention. Depression patients receiving EMDR Therapy showed significant differences in the post-test measurements of the Beck Depression Inventory (BDI) performed before and after therapy (27.26 ± 6.41 vs. 11.76 ± 3.71 , $p < 0.001$). In the study, a significant difference was found between the

post-test measurements of both groups (experimental group 11.76 ± 3.71 ; control group 31.66 ± 6.09 , $p < 0.001$). Research shows that EMDR Therapy is an effective and useful therapy approach in depressive disorder.

21. Pharmacological Interventions

There are conflicting results about the use of antipsychotic and mood stabilizer drugs in the high-risk group before disease development. Considering that these drugs have serious side effects, and the disease may not develop, their use is not recommended for now. However, it is recommended that young people diagnosed with bipolar disorder not otherwise specified should be treated using psychosocial and pharmacological methods together. The effects of nutritional or anti-inflammatory supplements such as omega-3 fatty acids, folic acid and aspirin on delaying disease development and reducing symptoms in high-risk groups are promising despite conflicting results. More studies are needed on this subject.

22. Female Bipolar Disorder

It keeps the gender gap and bipolar disorder in an area that needs even more attention. Studies investigating the effect of gender difference in bipolar disorder have been increasing in recent years. Comorbid physical illness, especially mixed episode and dysphoric states, depressive episode, rapid cycling, seasonal course, hypothyroidism, migraine attacks and obesity, are more common in women with bipolar disorder than in men. Although co-diagnosis of alcohol and substance use disorder is more common in male bipolar disorder cases, the risk of developing alcohol use and substance use disorder in females is higher than in male bipolar disorder cases. Women with bipolar disorder have special importance in terms of two life periods, during pregnancy and postpartum period, exacerbations, and relapses of bipolar disorder.

It should be noted that neuroimaging studies cause false results in comparisons between cases with schizophrenia and bipolar disorder, since the male gender has more

neurodevelopmental disorders. In a meta-analysis with groups matched for gender difference, it was determined that the anterior cingulate cortex (ACC) and posterior lateral prefrontal cortices of the subjects with schizophrenia in terms of gray matter reduction in the brain; ACC and frontoinsula cortices of bipolar disorder cases were found to be different from healthy controls.[17] There is no difference between genders in terms of gray matter volume in bipolar disorder cases. Decrease in anterior middle orbital prefrontal cortex gray matter volume and corresponding increase in amygdala gray matter volume have been defined as regional abnormalities responsible for emotional dysregulation in bipolar disorder cases. In the study of Almeida et al., amygdala and gray matter volume are within normal limits in bipolar disorder cases.[18] In this study, decreased gray matter volume in the left parahippocampal gyrus and putamen and bilateral posterior middle rectal gyrus was shown for the first time in bipolar disorder cases. Decreased gray matter volume in the left posterior middle rectal gyrus is associated with trait anxiety in male bipolar disorder cases. This region is where the middle prefrontal network responsible for somatomotor function and mood regulation is located.[18] With mental activity, salivary cortisol levels, which were found to be higher in women with bipolar disorder compared to men, were associated with the number of episodes with psychotic features in the whole group, and the number of depressive episodes in women.[19] In the same study, it was stated that salivary cortisol levels were higher in patients using antidepressants.

Bipolar disorder starts at a later age in females than in males.[20] Male gender and childhood antisocial behavior constitute a subgroup of early-onset bipolar disorder.[5] The frequency of first episode depression is higher among female bipolar disorder cases than males. In bipolar disorder, the time from the onset of the illness to the diagnosis is longer in females than in males. In addition, the diagnosis of these cases before the correct diagnosis was mostly unipolar depression.[21] There is no gender difference between late-onset unipolar and bipolar disorder cases.[22]

While the ongoing treatment compliance of female bipolar disorder patients is better than male patients, treatment compliance is worse in women with early onset and

living alone.[4] The frequency and severity of insight and mood swings affect treatment compliance in women. The relationship between treatment adherence and social support was stronger in female bipolar patients than in males. The relationship between treatment compliance and stigma is similar in all genders. Alcohol and substance use disorders impair treatment compliance in men more than women.

It should be known that pregnancy is not the only detail. Gender-specific differences in bipolar disorder also exist outside of pregnancy and post-pregnancy. These differences affect the clinical appearance and course of the disease in bipolar female cases, as well as the points to be considered in the treatment. The shaping of clinical and therapeutic approaches that include these differences will make an important contribution to individual-specific treatment.

23. Summary and Conclusion

a. Four key factors in bipolar disorder

- Genetic factors
- Cellular Structure - Familial Factors
- Triggering factors

As we mentioned above, the presence of psychiatric problems has increased remarkably in line with genetic and environmental factors. This has become an important public health problem, both individually and socially. Three-quarters of patients who apply for medical help have psychiatric problems that require urgent intervention. Bipolar disorder, one of the most common psychiatric disorders, is one of the leading mental disorders that cause significant disability in humans if left untreated.

b. Bipolar one and Bipolar 2 Disorder Symptoms

- The extreme highs and lows mentioned above as manic - The highs are known as manic and the lows are known as depressive episodes. - Extraordinary

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

energy in the person - Restlessness - Difficulty concentrating - Extreme happiness - Possible dangerous behaviors - Poor or insufficient sleep affecting life - Chronic fatigue - Irritability- Changes in sleep patterns- Changes in eating patterns- Suicidal ideation

c. Bipolar Disorder Symptoms

Sleep problems (decreased need for sleep)

Extremely elevated (euphoric) mood Increase in content of thinking and speech Increase in provocative and inappropriate behavior Increase in alcohol and substance use Increase in sexual desire Increased energy, activities, and restlessness Decreased concentration Spending a lot of money Having false beliefs about one's own abilities Decreased judgment capacity

The importance of early recognition of bipolar disorder, which was first defined in our country many years ago, and the sensitivity of all healthcare professionals to acute phase and maintenance treatment is obvious. In this way, treatment compliance, quality of life and social function of patients will increase.

24. References

- Eroğlu Zengin M, Özpoyraz N. Preventive treatment in bipolar disorder. *Current Approaches in Psychiatry* 2010; 2(2):206-36. (“ÖNEMLİ BİR RUH SAĞLIĞI SORUNU: BİPOLAR BOZUKLUK”)
- Miura T, Noma H, Furukawa TA, Mitsuyasu H, Tanaka S, Stockton S, Salanti G, et al. Comparative efficacy, and tolerability of pharmacological treatments in the maintenance treatment of bipolar disorder: a systematic review and network meta-analysis. *Lancet Psychiatry* 2014;1(5):351-9.
- Lindström L, Lindström E, Nilsson M, Hoistad M. Maintenance therapy with second generation antipsychotics for bipolar

- disorder - A systematic review and meta-analysis. *J Affect Disord.* 2017; 14;213:138-150.
- Akiskal HS. Classification, diagnosis, and boundaries of bipolar disorders: A review. In *Bipolar Disorders. WPA Series Evidence and Experience in Psychiatry* (Eds M Maj, HS Akiskal, JJ López-Ibor, N Sartorius): 1- 50. Chichester, Wiley, 2002.
- Angst J, Marneros A. Bipolarity from ancient to modern times: conception, birth, and rebirth. (“Psychotic and Bipolar Disorders - FP Essentials”) *J Affect Disord.* 2001; 67 (1-3): 3-19.
- APA. *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders.* 5th ed. Arlington: American Psychiatric Association; 2013.
- Baldassano CF, Marangell LB, Gyulai L, Ghaemi SN, Joffe H, Kim DR, Sagduyu K, et al. Gender differences in bipolar disorder: retrospective data from the first 500 STEP-BD participants. *Bipolar Disord* 2005; 7:465-470.
- Barnett JH, Smoller JW . The genetics of bipolar disorder. *neuroscience.* 2009; 164:331-43.
- Bebbington P, Ramana R. The epidemiology of bipolar disorder. *Soc Psychiatry Epid* 1995; 30:279-92 ,
- Begeley CE, Annegers JF, Swann AC, Lewis C, Coan S, Schnapp WB . The lifetime cost of bipolar disorder in the United States: an estimate based on incidence and course of illness. *Pharmacoeconomics* 2001; 19:483-495.
- Begley CE, Annegers JF, Swann AC, Lewis C, Coan S, Schnapp WB, et al. The lifetime cost of bipolar disorder in the US: an estimate for new cases in 1998. *Pharmacoeconomics.* 2001;19(5 Pt 1):483-95.
- Bellivier F, Golmard J, Rietschel M. Age at onset in Bipolar I Affective Disorder: further evidence for three subgroups. *Am J Psych* 2003; 160:999-1001.
- Bloch Y, Ratzoni G, Sobol D, Mendlovic S, Gal G, Levkovitz

- Y. Gender differences in electroconvulsive therapy: a retrospective chart review. *J Affect Disord* 2005; 84:99-102.
- Borch-Jacobsen M. Which came first, the condition or the drug ?. *London Review of Books*, 2010; 32 (19): 31-33.
- Brady RO Jr, McCarthy JM, Prescott AP, Jensen JE, Cooper AJ, Cohen BM, Renshaw PF, Ongur D. Brain gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA) abnormalities in bipolar disorder. *Bipolar Disord* 2013;15(4):434-9.
- Cashwell C, Nasson S. Building self-esteem of children and adolescents. *Journal of Humanistic Education & Development* 1997;36:59-68.
- Cederlöf M-, Larsson H-, Lichtenstein P, Almqvist C, Serlachius E, Ludvigsson JF. Nationwide populationbased cohort study of psychiatric disorders in individuals with Ehlers-Danlos syndrome or hypermobility syndrome and their siblings. ("Nationwide population-based cohort study of psychiatric disorders in ...") *BMC Psychiatry* 2016; four;16(1):207.
- Chatterton ML, Stockings E, Berk M, Barendregt JJ, Carter R, Mihalopoulos C. Psychosocial therapies for the adjunctive treatment of bipolar disorder in adults: network meta-analysis. *BrJ Psychiatry*. 2017 Feb 16. pii: bjp.bp .116.195321.
- "Dell'Osso L, Placidi GF, Nassi R, Freer P, Cassano GB, Akiskal HS." ("SciELO - Brasil - A clinical study comparing manic and mixed episodes ...") The manic-depressive mixed state: Familial, temperamental, and psychopathologic characteristics in 108 female inpatients. ("The manic-depressive mixed state: familial, temperamental and ...") *Eur Arch Psychiatry Clin Neurosci* 1991; 240: 234- 39.
- DSM IV diagnostic criteria handbook. trans. Ertuğrul Köroğlu, Physicians Publishing Union, Ankara, 179-182, 1994.

- Fagiolini A , Coluccia A, Maina G, Forgiore RN, Goracci A, Cuomo A. Diagnosis, Epidemiology and Management of Mixed States in Bipolar Disorder. *CNS Drugs*. 2015;29(9):725-40.
- Goodwin FK, Jamison KR. Manic-Depressive Illness. New York: Oxford University, 1990.
- Goodwin FK, Jamison KR.(Introduction) Manic-Depressive Illness. Bipolar Disorders and Recurrent Depression. 2nd Edition. Goodwin FK & Jamison KR. Oxford University Press, 2007.
- Goodwin RD, Jacobi F, Bittner A, Wittchen HU. The epidemiology of mood disorders. *T Oral (Trans. Ed.)*, Basic Book of Mood Disorders, Istanbul: Sigma Publishing, 2007, p.33-54.
- Grunze A, Meisenzahl E, Grunze H. Neuroimaging of bipolar disorders. *Fortschr Neurol Psychiatr* 2013 ;81 (Suppl 1):17-21.
- Güleç C, Köroğlu E. Basic Book of Psychiatry. 2nd Edition, Physicians Publishing Union, Ankara: Medico Graphics Printing House, 2007.
- Gureje O, Lasebikan VO, Kola L, Makanjuola VA. Lifetime and 12-month prevalence of mental disorders in the Nigerian Survey of Mental Health and well-being. *Br J Psychiatry* 2006; 188:465-71.
- Hendrick V, Altschuler LL, Gitlin MJ, Delrahim S, Hammen C. Gender, and bipolar illness. *J Clin Psychiatry* 2000; 61: 393-396.
- Hirschfeld RMA, Bowden CL, Gitlin MJ. Practice guideline for the treatment of patients with bipolar disorder. *AmJ Psychiatry*. 2002; 159(Suppl):1-35.
- Işık E. Depression and Bipolar Disorders. Istanbul: Visual Arts Press, 2003: 467-540.
- Judd LL, Akiskal HS. The prevalence and disability of bipolar spectrum disorders in the US population: Reanalysis of the ECA database considering subthreshold cases. *J Affect Disord* 2003; 73 (1-2): 123-131.

- Kaplan H, Saddock B. Bipolar Disorders. Comprehensive Textbook of Psychiatry. 7th Ed, 2000; 1284-1289.
- Kerner B. Genetics of bipolar disorder. Appl Clin Genet 2013; 7:33-42.
- "Kessler RC, Berglund P, Demler O, Jin R, Merikangas KR, Walters EE." ("Kessler RC, Berglund P, Demler O, Jin R, Merikangas KR, Walters EE ...") Lifetime prevalence and age-of-onset distributions of DSM-IV disorders in the National Comorbidity Survey Replication. Arch Gene Psychiatry 2005; 62(6):593-602.
- Köroğlu E. Mood Disorders: Ankara, Physicians Publication Association, 1996; 1: 429-448.
- Kriegshauser K, Sajatovic M, Jenkins JH, Cassidy KA, Muzina D, Fattal O et al. Gender differences in subjective experience and treatment of bipolar disorder. J Nerv Ment Dis 2010; 198:370-372.
- Kruger S, Cooke RG, Hasey GM, Jorna T, Persad E. Comorbidity of obsessive-compulsive disorder in bipolar disorder. J Affect Disord 1997; 34:117-120
- Lee YH. Psychiatric epidemiology in Korea. PartI:Gender and age differences in Seoul. J Nerv Ment Dis 1990; 178: 242-246.
- Mahmood T, Silverstone T Neuroendocrine challenge with a 5-HT(1D) receptor agonist differentiates between two subtypes of bipolar disorder according to polarity of onset. J Psychopharmacol. 2005;19(1):109-10.
- Maj M, Akiskal HS, Lopez-Ibor JJ, Sartorius N. Bipolar Disorders. West Sussex, UK, Wiley, 2002.
- Mandelli L, Souery D, Bartova L, Kasper S, Montgomery S, Zohar J, et al . ("Treatment for postpartum psychiatric disorders - SBU") Bipolar II disorder as a risk factor for postpartum depression.J Affect Disord 2016; 204:54-8.
- Merikangas KR, Akiskal HS, Angst J, Greenberg PE, Hirschfeld RM, Petukhova M, Kessler RC.

- "Lifetime and 12-Month Prevalence of Bipolar Spectrum Disorder in the National Comorbidity Survey Replication". Arch Gene Psychiatry 2007; 64(5): 543-552.
- Merikangas KR, Jin R, He JP, Kessler RC, Lee S, Sampson NA, Viana MC et al. Prevalence and correlates of bipolar spectrum disorder in the world mental health survey initiative. Arch Gene Psychiatry 2011;68(3):241-51.
- Montgomery SA, Cassano G. Management of bipolar disorder. Martin Dunitz Ltd. London, 1996.
- Mr. A, Aslan S. Relationship between mood disorders and temperament, character, and personality. ("Temperament and character predictors of depressed mood ... - Europe PMC") Turkish Journal of Psychiatry. 2005; 16:276-83.
- Oral T. Bipolar disorder. Istanbul: WPA series, CSA Medical Publication Agency, 2002;441-503.
- Patel NC, DelBello MP, Keck PE, Strakowski SM. Phenomenology associated with age at onset in patients with bipolar disorder at their first psychiatric hospitalization. Bipolar Disord 2006; 8:91-4.
- Pichot P. Circular insanity, 150 years on. Bulletin de l'Academie nationale de medicine 2004; 188 (2): 275-284. ("ÖNEMLİ BİR RUH SAĞLIĞI SORUNU: BİPOLAR BOZUKLUK")
- Post RM, Kupka R, Keck PE Jr, McElroy SL, Altshuler LL, Frye MA, Rowe M, et al. Further Evidence of a Cohort Effect in Bipolar Disorder: More Early Onsets and Family History of Psychiatric Illness in More Recent Epochs. J Clin Psychiatry 2016; doi: 10.4088/JCP.15m1012
- Rice J, Reich T, Nancy CA, Endicott J, Eerdewegh MV. The familial transmission of Bipolar Illness. Arch Gene Psychiatry 1987; 44:441-47.

- Sadock BJ, Sadock VA. Sadock & Sadock's Comprehensive Textbook of Psychiatry. Eighth edition, Ankara: Güneş Publishing House, 2007.
- Sedler MJ. Falret's discovery: The origin of the concept of bipolar affective illness. Translated by MJ Sedler and Eric C. Dessain. *Am J Psychiatry* 1983; 140 (9): 1127-1133.
- Shakibaei F, Alikhani M, Mahaki B, Sichani NK, Tabatabaei HD. The evaluation of mood condition among depressed adolescent students in Isfahan after 6 years. *Adv Biomed Res* 2016; thirty;5:94.
- Sobczak S, Honig A, Riedel WJ: Cautertryptophan depletion in bipolar disorders. *Acta neuropsychiatrica* two thousand; 12(3): 69-72.
- Stringaris A, Youngstrom E. Unpacking the differences in US/UK rates of clinical diagnoses of early-onset bipolar disorder. *Am Acad Child Adolesc Psychiatry*. 2014 Jun;53(6):609-11.
- Suominen K, Mantere O, Valtonen H, Arvilommi P, Leppamaki S, Isometsa E. Gender differences in bipolar disorder type I and II. *Acta Psychiatr Scand* 2009; 120:464-473.
- Suominen K, Mantere O, Valtonen H, Arvilommi P, Leppamaki S, Paunio T, Isometsa E. Early age onset of bipolar disorder is associated with more severe clinical features but delayed seeking treatment. *Bipolar Disord* 2007; 9: 698-705.
- Tondo L, Vázquez GH, Baldessarini RJ. Depression and Mania in Bipolar Disorder. *Curr Neuropharmacol* 2016; Jun 6.
- Uluşahin A. Genetics of bipolar disorder. *Journal of Psychiatry Psychology* 2004; twelve;(appendix 2) 31- 8.
- "Van der Voort TY, Seldenrijk A, van Meijel B, Goossens PJ, Beekman AT, Penninx BW, Kupka RW." ("Evidence for an enhanced procoagulant state in remitted major ...") *Functional versus*

- syndromal recovery in patients with major depressive disorder and bipolar disorder. *J Clin Psychiatry* 2015;76(6):e809-14.
56. Schaffer A, Isometsä ET, Tondo L, Moreno DH, Signor M, Kessing LV, Turecki G, et al. Epidemiology, neurobiology and pharmacological interventions related to suicide deaths and suicide tries in bipolar disorder. *Aust NZJ Psychiatry* 2015;49:785-802.
- van Enkhuizen J, Milienne-Petiot M, Geyer MA, Young JW. Modeling bipolar disorder in mice by increasing acetylcholine or dopamine: chronic lithium treats most, but not all features. *Psychopharmacology (Berl)* 2015;232(18):3455-67.
- Van Meter AR, Burke C, Youngstrom EA, Faedda GL, Correll CU. The Bipolar Prodrome: Meta-Analysis of Symptom Prevalence Prior to Initial or Recurrent Mood Episodes. *J Am Acad Child Adolesc Psychiatry* 2016;55(7):543-55.
- Vemuri M, Kenna HA, Wang PW, Ketter TA, Rasgon NL. Gender-specific lipid profiles in patients with bipolar disorder. *J Psychiatr Res* 2011; 45:1036-1041.